

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

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HELLENIC SOCIETY
OF MEDICAL
CHEMISTRY

19th

HELLENIC SYMPOSIUM on **Medicinal Chemistry**

HYBRID SYMPOSIUM

9-11 MARCH 2023

Conference and Cultural Center
of the University of Patras

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HELLENIC SYMPOSIUM
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9-11 March 2023

Welcome

The Organizing Committee cordially welcomes you at the **19th Hellenic Symposium on Medicinal Chemistry (HSMC-19)** organized on **March 9-11, 2023, in the University of Patras, Conference and Cultural Centre.**

The Symposium is organized by the **Hellenic Society of Medicinal Chemistry (HSMC)** and the **Section of Medicinal Chemistry-Pharmacognosy of the Department of Pharmacy, University of Patras.**

HSMC-19 continues the tradition of biannual meetings established since 30 years in Greece as a forum for the discussion of recent advances in the field of Medicinal Chemistry. The topics of the Symposium include Drug Design and lead identification and optimization, ADME/Tox properties in drug discovery, Advances in Synthetic Medicinal Chemistry, Natural Products, Chemical Biology, Pharmacology, Computational Chemistry, Chemoinformatics/Pharmaco-informatics, Pharmaceutical Analysis and -omics in Pharmaceutical Sciences are integrated to create the environment for fruitful interchange of ideas between scientists involved in Medicinal Chemistry related areas.

The official language of the Symposium is English.

The venue of the symposium is in the Conference and Cultural Centre of the University of Patras, a pole for international conferences and the main tool for the development of the cultural life of the region. Patras, the capital city of the Prefecture of Achaia and of the Region of Western Greece, is in the NW Peloponnese near Olympia and several other archeological sites; it has a population of a quarter of a million and is linked with all the major cities of Greece and Europe via land, sea and air. It is an interesting and attractive city where the archaeological sites are blended harmoniously with the contemporary and lively rhythms.

We welcome you and sincerely thank you for your active participation.

The Symposium Chairs

Prof. Emmanuel Mikros

President of the Hellenic Society of Medicinal Chemistry

Assoc. Professor Manolis Fouteris

Department of Pharmacy, University of Patras

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9-11 March 2023

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OF MEDICINAL
CHEMISTRY

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- Απλό στην χρήση
- Ευρύ πεδίο εφαρμογών
- Γρήγορη Ανάλυση
- Αξιόπιστα αποτελέσματα

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International Speakers

Karine Alvarez,
Aix Marseille University
(France)
Head of the "Medicinal Antiviral
Chemistry" thematic group

Maria Laura Bolognesi,
University of Bologna (Italy)
Coordinator of PhD Programme in
Biotechnological, Biocomputational,
Pharmaceutical and
Pharmacological Sciences

James D. Brien,
Saint Louis University (USA)
Assistant Professor in the
Molecular Microbiology &
Immunology Department

José Luis Marco Contelles,
Superior Council of Scientific,
Laboratory of Medicinal Chemistry
(Institute of General Organic
Chemistry, CSIC) (Spain)
Synthesis, Structure and Properties of
Organic Compounds (SEPCO)

Stefan Knapp,
Frankfurt University
(Germany)
Principal Investigator

Greek Speakers

Andreadou Ioanna, National Kapodistrian University of Athens
Fousteris Manolis, University of Patras
Georgakopoulos Konstantinos, National Kapodistrian University of Athens
Halabalaki Maria, National Kapodistrian University of Athens
Kokotos Christoforos, National Kapodistrian University of Athens
Kontogiorgis Christos, Democritus University of Thrace
Neochoritis Konstantinos, University of Crete
Orkoula Malvina, University of Patras
Papanastasiou Ioannis, National Kapodistrian University of Athens
Papazisis Georgios, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Pontiki Eleni, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Prousis Kyriakos, National Hellenic Research Foundation
Tzakos Andreas, University of Ioannina
Vidali Veroniki, National Centre For Scientific Research Demokritos
Zacharis Constantinos, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Zografos Alexandros, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

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HELLENIC SOCIETY
OF MEDICINAL
CHEMISTRY

The **Hellenic Society of Medical Chemistry (HSMC)**, founded in 1980, is active for more than 30 years, aiming to develop the science of Medicinal Chemistry in Greece.

HSMC promotes the dissemination and consolidation of the science of Medicinal Chemistry among the members of the academic and research community of the country. It strengthens the cooperation between medicinal chemists as well as their engagement with scientists of related fields and supports young scientists, particularly PhD candidates and Postdocs by providing scholarships to participate in scientific symposia and summer schools.

HSMC supports and undertakes the organization of national and international Symposiums in Greece, related to the field of Medicinal Chemistry.

HSMC is a member of the European Federation of Medicinal Chemistry (EFMC) and participates in the EFMC Council with an elected delegate. Also, it participates in EFMC committees, taking an active part in European medicinal chemistry activities.

We believe in the strong dynamic of Medicinal Chemistry research in Greece and we look forward to the support and active participation of all members in order to achieve the goals of the Hellenic Society of Medical Chemistry.

Enjoy your navigation on the website of the Hellenic Society of Medicinal Chemistry, www.hcmc.gr and join us!

Η φιλοσοφία της **BD Inventions** είναι να παρέχει τις πιο πρόσφατες και καινοτόμες τεχνολογίες που απαιτούνται από τους πελάτες μας για τη βελτίωση της αποδοτικότητάς τους.

Πρωταρχικός μας στόχος είναι να παρέχουμε προϊόντα και υπηρεσίες που ανταποκρίνονται και υπερβαίνουν τις απαιτήσεις των πελατών.

Τα κορυφαίας ποιότητας προϊόντα μας μαζί με την εξαιρετική τεχνική υποστήριξη βοηθούν τους πελάτες μας να επιτύχουν τους στόχους τους.

UNAUTHORISED SUBSTANCES IN FOOD SUPPLEMENTS - PHARMACEUTICALS

Amidžić Maja*, Banović Fuentes Jelena*, Torović Ljilja*

*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia

With the increase in popularity and number of food supplements on the market, the variety and number of related health risks also increases. A crucial element of a food safety system is rapid flow of information, in Europe operating through Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF).

Accordingly, RASFF database was automatically searched using the following criteria: category "dietetic food, food supplements, fortified foods", hazard category "composition" and period of assessment 2011-2022. Data related to selected classes of pharmaceuticals in food supplements were manually extracted, and evaluated.

Records showed hundreds of notifications related to pharmaceuticals and as the most "popular" for adulteration of food supplements have turned out to be in order: PDE-5 inhibitors with 235 notifications including sildenafil, tadalafil, vardenafil, avanafil and their synthetic analogues; anorexics and laxatives with 77 notifications including sibutramine along with its active metabolite N-didesmethyl sibutramine, phenolphthalein and 2,4- DNP (2,4-dinitrophenol); stimulants including natural phenethylamine (the most common in this group was synephrine with 50 notifications) and synthetic stimulants (the most common was 1,3 dimethylamylamine (DMAA) with 95 notifications); nootropic drugs including vinpocetine, vincamine and vinburnine with 24 notifications; anabolics with 16 notifications including pharmaceuticals as testosterone and stanozolol as well as its synthetic derivatives; cannabinoid cannabidiol (CBD) nowadays used as prescription drug for specific indications, but also pending authorization as novel food ingredient, with 14 notifications.

It is noteworthy that for a substantial number of supplements multiple non-compliance were recorded, meaning simultaneous presence of several unauthorized pharmaceuticals. The use of adulterated food supplements has led and will most likely lead to serious consequences for supplements' consumers, especially supplements adulterated with prescription drugs, where a number of cases of serious adverse events and even death were recorded.

What the health community can do in order to better protect public health is to put in an effort to improve analytical methodologies for the detection and structural identification of numerous derivatives of substances from different pharmacological classes as well as to create stricter legal regulations that will refer to the minimum safety requirements that producers must meet before commercializing the product.